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Culture and Ethics of the Driver

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The concepts of culture, professional culture and professional culture of drivers are used in science. Culture means the material and spiritual values created by mankind.

Professional culture is a high level of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for the successful implementation of a certain type of activity. The professional culture of drivers is an integral part of the universal culture. Based on this, drivers in their activities comply with the requirements of universal human culture and professional culture of the driver. By the professional culture of the driver, we understand that the person performing the service performs his duties at a high level from the point of view of law, morality and law. The professional culture of drivers includes a legal and moral culture, ideas about the social significance of a certain type of work. The main aspect of the professional culture of drivers is that it is normative in nature, that is, the requirements for the cultural image of drivers are determined by regulatory documents. The professional culture of drivers is reflected in their treatment of citizens, protection of the rights and interests of citizens, legislation, public order based on current laws, ethical and legal norms, and clothing.

In ensuring road safety, people are the main road users and take part as drivers, passengers, and pedestrians. Among them, the most important place is occupied by the driver. Therefore, when organizing traffic, it is necessary to take into account the psychological, physiological and biological capabilities of the driver.

Ethics is a philosophical science that studies moral issues, is considered one of the most important aspects of human life, and teaches a person the right way of life based on his own character. That is

why ethics includes the theory of human life, the study of emotions and at the same time teaching ways to achieve a prosperous life and happiness.

The ethics of the driver is manifested in his discipline, sense of responsibility, and moral qualities such as attitude to the team. Diligence, kindness to people, modesty are qualities characteristic of good and reliable people. Lack of interest in work, arrogance, rudeness, disrespect for others, disrespect for order and discipline, shows the qualities of a person prone to committing accidents. Indiscipline of drivers usually manifests itself in non-compliance with traffic rules on the roads. The driver must think not only about his own safety, but also about the safety of other road users. He only observes the behavior of others, without strictly following the rules.

For example, in cities, some drivers do not let pedestrians pass on the road, ignoring the requirement of the rule when turning. There are also cases when a driver, forced to let pedestrians pass, gets too close to them, honks and shouts. Many drivers behave as if there is no need to give warning signals or it is difficult to understand their behavior from the signals. There are cases when drivers are indifferent to road users when they get into an awkward situation or a difficult situation at an intersection. For example, in relation to a driver changing lanes, the second driver will shorten the distance instead of helping him by reducing speed and increasing the gap.

Sometimes the engine stalls before the intersection. In such cases, instead of understanding the situation of this driver and showing patience, insults, rudeness, even some drivers pass by, giving very loud and continuous beeps. It is not surprising that even the most experienced driver can get into such a predicament and get lost and confused by the attitude of the people around him. Therefore, any driver often finds himself in a situation where he needs the help of others. If the participants of the movement are polite to each other, friendly and ready to help, the number of accidents will be significantly reduced, and unpleasant accidents will be avoided. Alcohol consumption by a driver before starting to drive or on the road is the most serious and dangerous manifestation of indiscipline and imprudence. Such negative behavior is common in communities that do not monitor the actions of drivers.

After drinking alcohol or drugs, the ability to work decreases and the risk of driving increases. Human interaction is a very complex, delicate process that cannot be defined by specific patterns. In the process of driving a vehicle, which is considered a source of increased danger, the driver interacts to a certain extent with other drivers, passengers, pedestrians, and employees of state road safety authorities. In this regard, it is important to know that politeness on the roads is given serious attention. The basis for safe driving is created by the manners of drivers involved in traffic and their relationships with people around them. Drivers should pay attention to the culture of communication that affects passenger safety, that is, the culture of treating passengers and other people.

A society is a collection of people of different ages, different personalities, different professions and people of different nationalities. The psychology of interpersonal relations in public life originates from the communication of different people with each other, their participation in solving political and economic problems, in social work, creating material and spiritual benefits, their behavior at home and on the street, their mental development, condition and culture of behavior. Undoubtedly, the peculiarities of each nation have an impact on the emergence of the psychology of interpersonal relations. For example, the qualities characteristic of Uzbeks, such as respect for adults, unobtrusiveness and strict restraint, have a positive effect on the environment. Considering the above, the main focus of the driver is to have good relations with passengers and other people while driving,

to take precautions against pedestrians, especially children, the disabled, the elderly and cyclists, along with demonstrating one's professional ethics, it is one of the important factors in ensuring road safety.

Driving culture: definition and rules

The term "culture of drivers" refers to relations on public roads, generally characterizing the level of mutual relations and mutual revenue of all road users. It is assumed that the driver at the wheel complies with traffic regulations, does not create emergency situations and generally tries not to cause inconvenience to other drivers of vehicles and pedestrians.

There is a fairly large set of rules, which are called driving culture. Even a beginner is able to fulfill these unspoken prescriptions. Let's name only the main ones.

Compliance with traffic regulations is the first sign of respect for your colleagues. And even if one of them performed a strange maneuver himself, you should not be nervous and swear. It is better to try to understand what this driver will do next in order to prevent an emergency in advance.

When you see a faulty car on the side of the road, stop and offer help. Maybe you don't need it or you can't help. But in any case, showing sympathy and attention to the problems of others is a sign of good manners.

When parking, position your car so that it does not take up one and a half or two places. And even more so, do not "prop up" an already parked car. However, it happens that there are no other options left: then be sure to leave your phone number on a piece of paper under the glass.

If the car at the traffic light did not move too fast, do not signal persistently to this driver. After all, you can just "blink" the headlights – and he will understand everything without negative emotions.

When a problem is visible in a neighboring car, inform the car owner about it.

When approaching a traffic light with a red light or a traffic jam, skip cars that turn left. Personally, this will practically not detain you, you will still have to stand! But by blocking the way, you deprive your neighbors of at least a few minutes. The same applies to pedestrians at an intersection with a traffic jam: let people pass, and do not stand right at the crossing.

Driving ethics is not etiquette, but it helps on the road.

What is driving ethics? First of all, it is a set of moral rules of a person driving, that is, how he should behave. Violations of these rules are not fined or punished at all. However, excessive irritability, bad mood or aggressive driving style are the provocateurs of many unpleasant situations on the roadway.

Any of the unacceptable human qualities can lead to trouble. So, for some personal reasons, an aggressively minded driver commits a lot of dangerous actions. For example, he is clearly annoyed by the increased speed of the car that overtakes him, and the aggressor himself begins to violently press on the gas pedal, trying to "punish" the pseudo-offender at any cost. Conversely, when, according to all the rules, it is necessary to give way to a vehicle that has an unconditional advantage, it tries to "slip through" first.

Another sign of a person violating ethics is overtaking a car that is not moving fast enough in one lane despite traffic regulations. There are plenty of other situations when a violation of moral norms heats up the situation on the road.

Ideally, the moral relationship between the participants in the movement should consist of:

- refusal to drive under the influence of alcohol;

- a polite driving style, without "tearing", a sharp set of speed and emergency braking; the optimal style is a smooth start, gradual braking and rebuilding, early warning signals;
- the inadmissibility of taking revenge for the mistakes of others;
- using the safest driving techniques;
- maximum assistance to other road users;
- considerate and polite attitude towards pedestrians – after all, it can be a pregnant woman, an elderly person or a child;
- responsibility for your passengers;
- good technical condition of the vehicle and its appearance.

There are other, rather trivial, but effective rules of ethics that are prescribed to anyone driving, regardless of the cost of the car, driving experience and even the country of residence.

Effective ethics include:

1. Try to be understandable to others. To do this, you need to warn others about your maneuvers in advance, and not a couple of meters before turning at an intersection or stopping place. And do not delay the rebuilding, as well as do not carry it out abruptly: this is misleading other drivers, they do not understand what to expect from you in the future. And this is annoying...
2. Overtaking assistance is a sign of a friendly driver. How this rule is observed is demonstrated by truck drivers: if a queue of cars forms behind them, and the road is clear, they turn on the right signal; a left turn signal means that cars are driving in the oncoming lane, and overtaking should be postponed.
3. If the roadway narrows, follow the order of passage – "butting" in such areas is more expensive for yourself. That is why in some countries, in such cases, an algorithm for safe maneuvers is legally prescribed.
4. Help drivers trying to get out of side passages. After all, with heavy traffic, they will have to stand for quite a long time waiting for a break. And when the car driving in the front row slows down for at least a couple of seconds, it will help the waiting car to integrate into the stream.
5. It is better to turn on the low beam headlights at dusk, rather than in complete darkness. Even if it does not improve visibility, it definitely helps others to see your car in advance. And especially for pedestrians.
6. In general, the correct use of lighting devices is considered a sign of a true professional. For example, the "far distance" will never dazzle with a high beam, switching to the near one in time. And if a heavy-duty vehicle is approaching the top of the rise, then its driver turns on the near one a little earlier than the headlights of an oncoming car become visible.

Here are a few more rules that distinguish a polite driver:

- if you "get attached" to the leader car, immediately turn on the low beam so as not to dazzle the driver through the side mirrors;
- when they overtake you, turn off the high beam headlights as soon as the overtaking turns them on; accordingly, when you overtake yourself, turn on the high beam at the moment when you are level with the overtaken;

- if you stop, be sure to switch to dimensional lighting, which will improve the illumination of the roadway, and at the same time help drivers see your car. If the headlights are left on, they will blind other drivers of vehicles;
- you can talk about the culture of drivers for a very long time, but the best teacher is practice. Therefore, always consider how your actions affect other drivers. To paraphrase the “winged” expression: treat all road users the way you would like to be treated!

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